

ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS. PART III.
1-HYDROXY-2-NAPHTHOIC ACIDS IN THE ESTIMATION
OF ZIRCONIUM

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Analytical behaviour of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and its nitro and bromo derivatives was studied. Thorium and zirconium furnished quantitative precipitation with these acids. Gravimetric estimation of zirconium by these reagents and its separation from other elements have been described.

In a previous communication (*this Journal*, 1955, 32, 687), several phenolic acids were studied for their analytical applications, and most of them were found suitable in the determination of thorium and zirconium. In the present paper, the analytical behaviour of another phenolic acid, namely 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, and its derivatives, like 1-hydroxy-4-bromo-2-naphthoic and 1-hydroxy-4-nitro-2-naphthoic acids, has been examined. The preparation of these acids and their use in the quantitative estimation of zirconium and its separation from other elements are also described herein.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phenolic acids could be prepared by heating the sodium phenate in a stream of CO₂ (Kolbe, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1874, 10, 94). The method of Desai and Sethna (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 215) was modified a little in the present work for the preparation of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid.

Potassium bicarbonate (2 mol.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot water and α -naphthol (1 mol.) was gradually added to it with stirring to make a thick paste, and the mixture was heated in a glycerine bath, maintained at 120°-130°, in a slow current of CO₂. The heating was continued for 5 to 6 hours till the melt solidified. The mass was then poured into a beaker of water and stirred well till the solid was evenly distributed in water. The mixture was filtered to remove the unchanged α -naphthol. The filtrate was then acidified with HCl (dil.). 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid separated in the form of a pink precipitate which was crystallised from spirit till its melting point rose to 196°.

Derivatives of 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—The naphthoic acid (18.8 g.), dissolved in 100 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, was cooled in ice and to this mixture was added dropwise 18 g. of bromine (5%) in glacial acetic acid solution. The resulting blue-violet solution, which was kept under ice for 15 minutes, on pouring into water, produced a voluminous greyish violet precipitate. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and then boiled with water and the mixture was filtered hot. On cooling the filtrate shiny yellow crystals of 1-hydroxy-4-bromo-2-naphthoic acid separated, which was recrystallised from water, m.p. 130°. The residue (that remained on boiling with water) was discarded. It was a monobromo derivative. (Found: Br, 29.87. Calc. for C₁₁H₇O₃Br: Br, 29.96 per cent).

Fuming nitric acid (15 g.) was slowly added in small portions to a solution of the hydroxynaphthoic acid (15 g.) in alcohol (80%), well cooled in ice. The red-violet liquid was allowed to stand for 10 minutes in ice and then poured into a large volume of water; an ash-coloured precipitate appeared at once. This was filtered and washed with water till it was free of nitric acid. The precipitate was then boiled with water and the mixture was filtered hot. On cooling the filtrate, a yellow coloured solid came out. This was recrystallised from hot water, m.p. 165°, (decomp. 200°) and was identified to be the 1-hydroxy-4-nitro-2-naphthoic acid. (Found : N, 5.87. Calc. for $C_{11}H_7O_3N$: N, 6.0 per cent).

Possible Use in Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis

It was observed that 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid developed a bluish violet coloration with copper and blue coloration with Fe^{III} at p_H 3.09. The nitro and bromo compounds produced bluish green colour with copper and yellow-green and bluish green respectively, with iron at the same p_H . All the three acids developed orange coloration with uranium at p_H 3.61. They produced white or yellowish white precipitates with Hg^I , the precipitation, however, was not complete. Quantitative precipitations of thorium and zirconium were obtained with all these acids at p_H 4.58. The thorium salts of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and its nitro and bromo derivatives are white, yellowish white and orange, respectively, while those of zirconium are white, yellow and brown.

Gravimetric Determination of Zirconium

A standard stock solution of zirconium nitrate (Merck's reagent quality) was prepared and the zirconium content was determined with benzilic acid (Venkatramaniah and Rao, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 257; Klingenberg and Mendel, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 754). Stock solutions of various metal salts (all reagent grade), like iron (ic), barium, calcium, strontium, cobalt, nickel, chromium, manganese, titanium and uranium were also prepared and their metal content was estimated by standard methods.

1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid is sparingly soluble in water. Its 0.5% solution was prepared in boiling water. Cold aqueous solution (2%) of its sodium salt was also used. The bromo and nitro derivatives were more soluble in hot water than the parent substance, so their 1% solutions in hot water were used for estimations.

Procedure.—Aliquot quantities of zirconium solutions, rendered neutral to Congo red, were heated nearly to boiling and then the reagent solutions in slight excess were added. No immediate precipitate appeared, but on adding about 1 c.c. of 2% ammonium acetate solution precipitation occurred at once. 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid afforded a white flocculent precipitate; the nitro and bromo derivatives produced yellow and brown gelatinous precipitates respectively. On heating the beaker for a few minutes the precipitates collected in the form of easily filtrable mass towards the centre of the beaker. In no case the precipitates should be boiled. The nature of the precipitates obtained with the sodium salt of hydroxynaphthoic acid was much better than that with the free acid. The precipitate was filtered and washed with hot water several times and then ignited to zirconia to a constant weight. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Estimation of zirconium with hydroxynaphthoic acid.

No.	ZrO ₂ taken.	ZrO ₂ found by			
		1-OH-N.	Na-salt of 1-OH-N.	1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N.	1-OH-4-Br-N.
1	0.0462 g.	0.0461 g.	0.0462 g.	0.0461 g.	0.0464 g.
2	0.0308	0.0308	0.0310	0.0308	0.0310
3	0.0231	0.0229	0.0231	0.0233	0.0233
4	0.0154	0.0150	0.0151	0.0152	0.0153
5	0.0077	0.0072	0.0074	0.0075	0.0077
6	0.0039	0.0023	0.0028	0.0030	0.0032
7	0.0119	...	...	0.0015	0.0017

N stands for naphthoic acid.

From the above table it is evident that the bromo derivative is the most effective precipitating agent of all the reagents, then come nitro compound, sodium salt of hydroxynaphthoic acid and the free hydroxynaphthoic acid in the decreasing order of effectiveness.

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration on the Precipitation of Zirconium.—With a view to ascertaining a suitable p_H range for each of the reagents, for the quantitative precipitation of zirconium, estimations were carried out in a similar manner in solutions having different p_H values. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

ZrO₂ taken = 0.0154 g.

ZrO ₂ found (g.) by	p_H of the final solutions.					
	3.	3.6.	4.2.	4.8.	5.0	5.5
1-OH-N	0.0120	0.0144	0.0152	0.0153	0.0152	0.0153
1-OH-N (Na salt)	0.0129	0.0147	0.0153	0.0154	0.0155	0.0156
1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N	0.0130	0.0150	0.0152	0.0154	0.0155	0.0156
1-OH-4-Br-N	0.0141	0.0152	0.0154	0.0155	0.0155	0.0156

It is seen from the p_H studies that the bromo derivative has a very wide range of p_H , i. e. from 3.6 to 5.5, for the quantitative precipitation of zirconium, while the range for the others is too narrow.

Separation of Zirconium from Foreign Ions

In order to study the interference by other metals, different quantities of metal solutions were added to a definite amount of zirconium nitrate solution and the precipitation of zirconium was carried out as before. Separation from most of the metals, like Ca, Ba, Sr, Al, Zn, Mg, Ti etc., may be carried out with these reagents by single precipitation, whereas iron, cobalt, nickel and uranium require double precipitation. As thorium is co-precipitated by all these reagents, within the same range as zirconium, it is not possible to separate Zr from Th. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

ZrO ₂ taken.	Metal oxide added.	ZrO ₂ found by		
		← 1-OH-N (Na-salt).	1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N.	→ 1-OH-4-Br-N.
0.0231 g.	CaO 0.0316 g.	0.0230 g.	0.0230 g.	0.0231 g.
"	BaO 0.0250	0.0231	0.0232	0.0232
"	SrO 0.0218	0.0230	0.0231	0.0233
"	* Fe ₂ O ₃ 0.0181	0.0238	0.0236	0.0235
"	Al ₂ O ₃ 0.0232	0.0233	0.0232	0.0232
0.0154	ZnO 0.0153	0.0151	0.0152	0.0153
"	MgO 0.0190	0.0152	0.0152	0.0153
"	TiO ₂ 0.0252	0.0151	0.0152	0.0154
"	* CoO 0.0167	0.0156	0.0156	0.0155
"	* NiO 0.0266	0.0157	0.0156	0.0155
"	* U ₃ O ₈ 0.0157	0.0156	0.0155	0.0155

* Indicate double pptn.

Composition of Zirconium Salts

The zirconium salts of all the acids were prepared as before; they were washed with boiling water several times and then with hot alcohol in order to free them from organic acids, and finally with ether. They were dried in an electric oven at 110°-115° to constant weights. Aliquot amounts of these salts were ignited in a platinum crucible and weighed as ZrO₂. The results of analysis show that zirconium cannot be estimated by direct weighing with any of these acids, as the salts are all basic in nature. One atom of zirconium is associated with three hydroxyl groups and one acid residue in a molecule of all the salts.

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